

Recommendation 22:

Using 'Smart Workplace' to meet the business need 'Talent acquisition and retention; Simplifying recruitment procedures'

Actual solutions and services:

According to a CBRE foresight study in 2040 e.g. the following properties will characterize a smart workplace:

- Flexible working contracts (increase mobility and unconventional working patterns)
- "wellness" services at the workplace
- Focus on collaboration

Many employees prefer to have a mobile working environment and mobile solutions to help them to improve their work-life-balance. Thus many mobile solutions (like smartphones & tablets, wearables, cloud computing) would help to attract new talents.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency and productivity. • Greater employee commitment. • Competitive advantage. • Higher degree of collaboration. • Multiple channels of communication. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High setup costs. • Skilled personnel/employees required.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better work-life balance. • Higher environmental sustainability. 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to change. • Bureaucracy • Privatisation of Public Assets

Talent acquisition and retention; Simplifying recruitment procedures:

This need pertains to recruiting talented employees and skilled staff, and retaining them by providing talent enhancement programs. The specific sub needs that emerged through our desk research are: attract skilled workers, STEM-skilled (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) workforce and enhance talent of existing employees . Our informant mentioned, " Stop brain drain of young talents."

Smart Workplace:

*A Smart or High Performance Workplace is a physical or virtual environment designed to make workers as effective as possible in supporting business goals and providing value. Such a workplace results from continually balancing investment in people, process, physical environment and technology, to measurably enhance the ability of workers to learn, discover, innovate, team and lead, and to achieve efficiency and financial benefit.**

*Gartner IT Glossary, High Performance Workplace, <http://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/high-performance-workplace>
TechRepublic, Gartner Hype Cycle: Exploring the leading-edge technologies for a digital business,
<http://www.techrepublic.com/article/gartner-hype-cycle-exploring-the-leading-edge-technologies-for-a-digital-business/>